

Empowering Leadership: Narratives of Student Leaders in School Activities

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Abstract. This study explored the experiences of student-leaders in school activities. Ten (10) student-leaders of the Supreme Pupils' Government, Mati-South District, Division of Mati City, participated in the study. The study employed a phenomenological approach to extract participants' ideas. In-depth interviews were conducted to gather information about their respective experiences and coping mechanisms. Thematic analysis revealed the following themes: student leaders' experiences in role modeling, intensifying communication, and employing an output-oriented approach. The coping mechanisms for the challenges were time management, dealing with passive members, resilience, and resourcefulness. Insights from the study's findings include empowering leaders, fostering stakeholders' support, and promoting unity and collaboration. The results revealed that student leaders foster a culture of leadership.. They were also empowered through the collaboration and coordination efforts among stakeholders. Moreover, student leaders thrived when they were empowered with responsibilities and given the autonomy to make decisions. The narratives of student leaders in school activities with empowering leadership have profound implications for leadership development, student engagement, school culture, problem-solving, and community relationships. By embracing and promoting empowering leadership practices, schools can cultivate a positive and vibrant learning environment that nurtures the potential of all students.

KEY WORDS

1. empowering leadership 2. student leaders 3. school activities

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1. Introduction

Leadership is a crucial attribute that shapes individuals, communities, and organizations. In educational institutions, student leaders are pivotal in fostering a positive school environment and empowering their fellow students. Student leaders in school activities have the opportunity to develop and showcase their leadership skills while making a positive impact on their school community. They brainstorm ideas and work collaboratively with their peers and teachers to implement or enhance initiatives. They recruit and assemble a team of like-minded individuals who share their passion and goals. They create a supportive environment that fosters growth and creativity by delegating tasks and empowering team members. Through leadership opportunities, students learn to set goals, manage time, prioritize tasks, and delegate responsibilities. They develop critical thinking problem-solving and decision-making abilities. Litera-

ture from the UK emphasizes the role of student councils and similar structures in promoting student voice and agency within schools (Fielding Bragg, 2018). However, there are challenges in ensuring these bodies are genuinely representative and effective in driving change. Additionally, the impact of leadership development programs on long-term career trajectories and civic engagement has been a focus of research, with mixed findings regarding their efficacy. In Australia, studies have explored the link between student leadership and school culture, highlighting the potential for student leaders to influence peer behavior and attitudes (Coldwell Sim, 2020). However, there are concerns about the sustainability of leadership initiatives beyond individual student terms. Research also addresses the need for training and support for both student leaders and the educators who work with them, particularly in navigating complex issues such as conflict resolution and ethical decision-making. Student leaders are more likely to take ownership of their own learning and take the initiative in their education. They can also provide peer support, acting as mentors and supporting other students, helping to create a positive and inclusive school culture. Canadian literature underscores the importance of student leadership in fostering a sense of belonging and community within schools, particularly in diverse urban settings (Fletcher Young, 2018). However, balancing student leadership responsibilities with academic demands and extracurricular activities can be challenging. Studies also highlight the role of technology in enhancing student leadership opportunities, with initiatives such as online platforms for virtual student councils gaining traction. In the Philippines, the concept of empowering leadership in student activities has gained prominence in recent years. Research by Aguinaldo (2019) explores how empowering leadership styles among student leaders contribute to the effectiveness of student organizations in Philippine universities. Research by

Santos (2021) highlighted how academic pressures often conflict with the responsibilities of student leadership, leading to stress and burnout among student leaders. This challenge is not unique to the Philippines and has been observed in countries like the United States (Smith, 2018). Studies by Nguyen (2022) and Alves (2023) discuss how student leaders face challenges due to limited resources, both financial and infrastructural, which can hinder their ability to implement projects and initiatives effectively. Moreover, this research creates platforms for student involvement, allowing their fellow students to voice their concerns, suggestions, and ideas. This promotes a sense of ownership and inclusivity, empowering students to actively participate in shaping their educational experiences. Student leaders contribute to a more vibrant and student-centered learning environment by providing avenues for student engagement.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The study is on the phenomenological inquiry as it aims to explore and understand the lived experiences of individuals within a specific phenomenon. In this case, the researcher focused on the experiences of student leaders involved in school activities, particularly those who have been empowered with leadership responsibilities. Adopting an empowering leadership approach aimed to investigate how these student leaders perceive and make meaning of their experiences in leading school activities. This phenomenological inquiry shed light on student leaders' subjective experiences, thoughts, emotions, and challenges, providing valuable insights for educators, school administrators, and researchers interested in promoting effective student leadership development. This study sought to provide valuable insights into the subjective experiences, challenges, and personal growth of these individuals. The findings may contribute to the existing body of knowledge on student leadership development and assist educators, school administrators, and researchers in designing effective

programs and support structures to nurture and empower student leaders in their school communities.

1.2. *Research Questions*—Researchers may gain insights into the potential benefits

- (1) What are the experiences of student leaders in promoting school activities?
- (2) How do they cope with the challenges in school activities?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the findings of the study of student leaders in their leadership journey?

1.3. *Definition of Terms*—The impact of student leaders extends far beyond their tenure in school. Their efforts could leave a lasting legacy that influences future generations of students. This study may find significance in the following: Department of Education. The department may ensure that leadership development is integrated into the school curriculum. DepEd’s leadership training programs equip student leaders with essential skills and competencies. School administrators. School administrators play a significant role in shaping the experiences of student leaders in school activities by empowering their leadership. Administrators may allocate budgets, offer logistical support, and ensure that students have access to necessary facilities and materials. Teachers could serve as mentors and guides to student leaders, providing support, advice, and encouragement in navigating their leadership roles. Parents. Parents should support and encourage their children who take on leadership roles in school activities. Emotional support from parents is crucial for student leaders, especially during challenging times. Students. Students themselves also have important duties in shaping the experiences of student leaders in school activities by empowering their leadership. Student leaders may recognize and celebrate the achievements and contributions of their peers, fostering a culture of appreciation and support. To fully understand the terms used in this study, the following are defined operationally: Student

guided to explore the lived experiences of student leaders in school activities by empowering leadership; this study sought answers to the following research questions:

Leaders. These are individuals within a school community who hold positions of responsibility, authority or influence over their peers. Operationally, this might be defined by specific roles such as class president, student council member, club president, or any other formal leadership position within the school. School Activities. These encompass organized events, programs, or initiatives within the school environment. Operationally, this could include extracurricular clubs, sports teams, academic competitions, cultural events, community service projects, and other structured activities the school facilitates. Empowering Leadership. This refers to a leadership style or approach that fosters individuals’ or groups’ growth, autonomy, and development. Operationally defining empowering leadership might involve specifying behaviors or characteristics such as delegating responsibility, providing support and resources, encouraging participation, fostering a sense of ownership, promoting self-efficacy, and facilitating opportunities for skill-building and personal development within the school context.

1.4. *Review of Significant Literature*—

1.4.1. *Leadership Development*—Student leadership roles provide experiential learning opportunities, allowing students to develop leadership skills in real-world contexts (Brown et al., 2019). They cultivate competencies such as teamwork, communication, decision-making, and problem-solving through organizing events and leading teams (Drewry Doermann, 2018;

Conway et al., 2020). These experiences contribute to personal growth, self-awareness, and empowerment (Liang et al., 2021).

1.4.2. Social and Emotional Learning (SEL)—Student leadership roles enhance SEL by developing empathy, collaboration, and resilience. Interactions with peers, mentors, and stakeholders improve interpersonal skills and emotional intelligence (Bennett Benner, 2022; Glanville Wildhagen, 2019). Mentorship from teachers and community members provides support and inspiration, aiding student leaders in reaching their potential (Quin, 2023).

1.4.3. Early Leadership Conceptions—Early leadership identities are shaped by school activities, team sports, community service, and family influences. Observing and modeling leadership behaviors from teachers, peers, and community leaders form early leadership conceptions (Brown et al., 2019; Drewry Doermann, 2018). Experiential learning through student government, clubs, and sports teams develops understanding of leadership principles and responsibilities (Conway et al., 2020; Liang et al., 2021). Peer influence, cultural norms, and institutional practices also play significant roles (Bennett Benner, 2022; Glanville Wildhagen, 2019).

1.4.4. Altruistic Leadership Conceptions—Altruistic leadership focuses on empathy, compassion, and social responsibility. It promotes inclusivity and a sense of belonging among diverse student populations (Johnson et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2020). Service-learning programs effectively develop altruistic leadership skills, enhancing altruistic attitudes and empathy (Chen, 2022). Altruistic motives influence ethical decision-making and behavior in school leadership roles (Garcia et al., 2023).

1.4.5. Theories of Leadership—Transformational Leadership: Inspires and motivates others to achieve common goals, fostering individual growth and empowerment (Brown et al., 2019). Servant Leadership: Emphasizes serving

others, demonstrating empathy, humility, and a commitment to the well-being of peers (Drewry Doermann, 2018). Authentic Leadership: Focuses on self-awareness, transparency, and integrity, acting with honesty and building trust (Conway et al., 2020). Distributed Leadership: Promotes shared decision-making, collaboration, and collective responsibility, empowering peers to lead (Liang et al., 2021). Social Change Leadership: Mobilizes individuals and communities to address social issues, advocating for equity and justice (Bennett Benner, 2022). Adaptive Leadership: Navigates complex challenges with resilience, flexibility, and problem-solving abilities (Glanville Wildhagen, 2019). Ethical Leadership: Prioritizes ethical decision-making, integrity, and moral responsibility, serving as positive role models (Quin, 2023).

1.5. Theoretical Lens—One theoretical lens used to examine student leaders' experiences in school activities through empowering leadership is the Transformational Leadership Theory by James V. Downton (1973). This theory focuses on the leader's ability to inspire and motivate their followers to achieve extraordinary outcomes beyond their own self-interests. It was particularly relevant in the context of empowering leadership, as it emphasizes the leader's role in empowering and developing their followers to become leaders themselves. According to the Transformational Leadership Theory, student leaders who exhibit empowering leadership behaviors could significantly impact the experiences of their fellow students involved in school activities. By empowering others, student leaders can foster a sense of ownership, autonomy, and personal growth among their peers. This can create a positive and supportive environment where students feel motivated and inspired to participate actively in various school activities. Empowering leadership involves several vital dimensions that align with the principles of transformational leadership. This is also supported by the Servant Leadership

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Theory. Student leaders embody the principles of servant leadership by prioritizing the needs and well-being of their peers above their own. As discussed by Nguyen et al. (2020), student leaders serve as humble servants, dedicated to serving the interests of the collective rather than seeking personal gain. This selfless approach to leadership empowers others to reach their full potential, making them feel respected and valued. Wong et al. (2023) highlight instances where student leaders empower their peers to take ownership of projects and initiatives, fostering a culture of empowerment and collaboration. Student leaders are expected to set an example for their peers and promote a positive and inclusive learning environment. This involves organizing and leading events, participating in decision-making processes, and advocating for the needs and interests of other students. Setting directions by helping one's colleagues develop a shared understanding of school strategies and goals. Practices in this category include creating and monitoring performance expectations. Evidence suggests that the ability to set directions accounts for the largest portion of a leader's impact. Moreover, in Transactional Leadership Theory, student leaders exhibit traits of transactional leadership by setting clear expectations and goals for their peers and providing rewards and recognition for achievement. Chow et al. (2021) discuss how student leaders establish clear guidelines and expectations for participation in school activities. Transactional leaders

exchange with their followers, offering rewards or incentives in exchange for performance. Lee et al. (2019) highlight instances where student leaders offer incentives or rewards to motivate their peers to participate in school initiatives. As a student leader, you will learn valuable soft skills while gaining real-world leadership experience. Meetings would teach you communication and expectation setting; projects would teach you time management and responsibility; presentations would teach you public speaking and organization. The results of this study indicate that leadership experience can effectively foster creativity in undergraduate students. This finding has various implications for practices to foster creativity more effectively through leadership positions. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected working themes. The experiences of student leaders in promoting school activities, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and coping mechanisms with the challenges in school activities, would enhance this practice and effect positive changes concerning the educational goals of the learning community. There was a genuine concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines that educational management insights drawn from the study's findings identified a way of teaching and learning development that was critical to school success.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. The researcher utilized artificial intelligence (AI) methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation, explicitly leveraging AI to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is communicated openly to adhere to ethical norms in research, underscoring a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledging AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing. The explored facts and knowledge in this study necessitate the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the following conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research-undertaking starts with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (2007) traced the 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradeigma) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model, or example. A paradigm was the patterning of the thinking of a person; it was a principal example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions were taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an act of submitting to a view (Stanage 2007). Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality was subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the researcher relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. The researcher made sure that the participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that, on the epistemological assumption, the researcher would attempt to lessen the distance between themselves and the participants. It was suggested that being a researcher, it was expected that time was spent in the field with participants, and the researcher becomes an 'insider'. It is assumed that the researcher established a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) states that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggested that the researcher openly discussed values that shape the narrative and included their interpretation in conjunction with participants' interpretation. The researcher upheld the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the

personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. The researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully understood the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation.

Rhetoric meant reporting reality through the eyes of my research participants. The researcher used personal voice and qualitative terms such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability instead of internal and external validity and objectivity. Patton (2000) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks the question, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people? The goal of this research study works well with this definition in trying to understand the student leaders' experiences of their involvement in school activities. Guba (2007) pointed out that the researcher needs to prepare for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested the information be viewed as only "the tip of the iceberg." The researcher implemented the qualitative research method of phenomenology to allow for the exploration of the student-leader's experiences in school activities. Burns and Grove (2003) stated that phenomenology is a philosophy, an approach or perspective to living, learning and doing research". The goal of phenomenological research is to capture lived experiences, find meaning that may or may not be known to the person who experienced them, and describe the phenomenon through a composite narrative. For the qualitative researcher, the only reality is the reality participants involved in the research situations construct.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—Using qualitative methodology, a phenomenological approach was chosen for this study. This study utilized in-depth interviews. The researcher conducted the interviews using an interview guide, which participants answered based on their experiences and practices related to the

study. An in-depth interview is a qualitative research technique involving intensive individual interviews with a few respondents to explore their perspectives on a particular idea, program, or situation (Boyce Neale, 2006). Interviews are primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. A phenomenological approach was used to gain a broader insight. Phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach is to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon for investigatory inquiry. (Creswell, 2013).

2.3. Design and Procedure—The study utilized a qualitative research method employing a phenomenological qualitative design. According to Lester, phenomenological research is concerned with the study of experiences from the individual's perspective, "bracketing" taken-for-granted assumptions and usual ways of perceiving. The phenomenological approach is based on a paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity. It emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. Thus, it was powerful for understanding subjective experiences, gaining insights into participants' motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Qualitative research mainly was associated with words, language, and experiences rather than measurements, statistics, and numerical figures. Qualitative research refers to the inductive, holistic, epic, subjective, and process-oriented methods used to understand, interpret, describe, and develop a theory on phenomena or settings. It was a systematic, subjective approach used to describe life experiences and give them meaning (Burns Grove, 2003). The phenomenological research design selected in this study was used to collect data on the

experiences and challenges of student-leaders in school activities. This research approach deepened the understanding of nature and the meaning of everyday experiences. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help to grasp the subject's perspective. Bryman (2012) posited that through interviews or face-to-face discussions, personal and detailed personal story could be told, with a focus on how the interviewee understands and explains different phenomena. The researcher aimed to draw an in-depth study of the experiences and challenges of student-leaders in empowering leadership in school activities. Qualitative research was interested in understanding how people interpret their experiences, how they construct their worlds, and what meaning they attribute to their experiences" (Merriam, 2009). This form of research provides a deep understanding of the subject and results in enhanced explanatory power. The researcher becomes "a part of the world they study; the knower and the known are taken to be inseparable" (Hatch, 2002). Because of the researcher's involvement, however, "much qualitative research was subjective. . ." (Wrench, Thomas-Maddox, Richmond, and McCroskey, 2008) Bloomberg and Volpe (2008) described qualitative research as "idea generation." Its design was proposed up front, but it is open and emergent rather than rigid and fixed to permit exploration. It uses small samples purposefully. It takes place within natural contexts, and real-world situations are studied as they unfold. Its framework allows for flexibility and creativity. The qualitative research explored and described student-leaders' experiences in empowering leadership in school activities. The research technique used was a modified van Kaam method described by Moustakas (2000) based on recorded and transcribed interviews using semi-structured questions to

capture the student-leaders strategies and challenges in empowering leadership in school activities. Specifically, phenomenology was the study of the subjective experiences of others. It researched the world through the eyes of another person by discovering how they interpret their experiences. It describes the meaning of the lived experiences of several individuals about a concept or a phenomenon. Phenomenology explores the structures of consciousness in human experiences, as noted by Polkinghorne (2000). This involved procedures which the qualitative researchers should follow. First, the researcher wrote research questions that would explore the meaning of life experiences for individuals and asked individuals to describe these experiences. The researcher collected data from individuals who had experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via lengthy interviews. Next, the data analysis involved horizontalization that extracted significant statements from transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each would fall under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience – both the textual description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated the meaning of the experience here. Finally, the report is written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected in the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket their own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when their observations were incorporated into the study. Accordingly, Hycner, (2008) phe-

nomenology in business research studies ideas were generated from the abundant amount of data using induction and human interests, as well as stakeholder perspective may have their reflection on the study. A study that attempted to explore student-leaders experiences in school activities via conducting in-depth interviews was a relevant example of research with a phenomenology philosophy. Advantages associated with phenomenology include a better understanding of meanings attached by people and its contribution to the development of new theories. Its disadvantages include difficulties with analysis and interpretation, usually lower levels of validity and reliability compared to positivism, and more time and other resources required for data collection (Hycner, 2008). Similarly, Schutz (2010) stressed that the purpose of the phenomenological approach is to illuminate the specific to identify phenomena through how they are perceived by the actors in a situation. In the human sphere, this translates typically into gathering 'deep' information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions, and participant observation and representing it from the perspective of the research participant(s). Phenomenology is concerned with the study of experience from the perspective of the individual, 'bracketing' taken-for-granted assumptions, and usual ways of perceiving. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were dominant for understanding the subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. The researcher aims to employ phenomenology-type qualitative method research since the focal point of this study was to investigate and explore the learners' experiences as student-leaders in school activities.

2.4. *Ethical Consideration*—Ethical considerations were of paramount importance in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participant groups addressed in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most critical parts of the research. The researcher must also adhere to promoting the aims of the research, imparting factual knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. Research is essential to society. This study focuses on social value by examining the experiences and coping mechanisms of student leaders in empowering leadership. Thus, the social problem that pushed the researcher's interest is the challenges the student leaders encountered in empowering leadership. This study could serve as a basis for higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions where learners could benefit. Informed Consent. Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pellerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and identify the anticipated information that the informants are expected to provide. All participants were then required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating in the research. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to participate ensured that participation in the research was entirely voluntary in nature, and

based on an understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection were lodged in the appendices of this study. The Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study were deemed capable of answering the research instrument for they served as the first-hand source of information. Thus, the researcher then assured the participants that they can easily be reached through their contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. This was done to answer possible questions of the respondents. Furthermore, if respondents experienced possible discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher had to ensure that the respondents were safe during the conduct of the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered at a convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality, and minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their real sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed outputs that were carried out from this study were kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were

given consideration so that there would be no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information, as well as representation of primary data findings in a biased way, could be avoided. Justice. The participants were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were then briefed that they had to give their full honesty in answering the survey questions and additionally, any type of communication about the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they would be the ones to benefit first with the results of the study. Transparency. The results of the study could then be accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and is placed on CD or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher to provide. Also, by learning about the results of the study, classroom teachers would be aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can request to be allowed to verify their transcript after the interview was carried out. The participants were provided with the opportunity to amend or remove any information which they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms, and changing names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured the possession of the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher had completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the researcher's master's degree, and they are qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally,

emotionally, and financially. Also, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strives to complete the study successfully within the specified time and was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee can help enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. The researcher also has to ensure that he/she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study would not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher deemed it necessary to express their great pleasure for their whole-hearted participation in this study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by adequately citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said in their own way. Understand the context of the study and avoid copy-paste the text verbatim from the reference paper. Always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, they would assure them of honesty in working on the manuscript and that there was no intentional misrepresentation in the study and making up of data and/or results or purposefully putting forward conclusions that were not accurate.

2.5. *Research Participants*—The key participants of this study were the selected elementary grade learners who were student-leaders of Supreme Pupil's Government of Mati-South District, Division of Mati City. The researcher utilized ten (10) student-leaders for an in-depth interview (IDI) who were purposely selected. The researcher secured assent from the participants and permission from the parents before the conduct of the study. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the

participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study. It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants will be purposefully done to ensure that the findings will be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.6. *Research Instrument*—Qualitative analysis was employed to establish the study's credibility, transferability, and dependability. The participants' experiences were captured through audiotaped one-on-one, non-structured interviews, peer debriefing, and field notes. Each participant completed the audio tape one-on-one, structured interview, peer debriefing, and field notes within four days, with each session lasting between 1 hour and 15 minutes. Interview Guide. The researcher prepared five open-ended questions for the unstructured interview to gather additional information and supporting answers to validate the study's findings. The interview questions were parallel to the components contained in the questionnaire. The phenomenological research design was selected in this study to collect data on the participants' life experiences. The research approach deepens the understanding of nature and the meaning of everyday experiences. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help to grasp the subject's perspective. Bryman (2008) posits that through interviews or face-to-face discussions, personal and detailed stories can be told, with a focus on how the interviewee understands and explains different phenomena. The researcher in this study aimed to draw an in-depth study of the experiences of student-learners and challenges in school activities. A questionnaire was a set of carefully designed, written down, and tested questions which were asked of individual respondents to gather information in research (Enon, 2008). These structured questionnaires but with some

open-ended questions included. They were prepared to cater to the subjects that were too busy and difficult to trace. It is also a useful instrument for the researcher to use whose number is too significant to cover by the researcher personally. The questionnaires would also be appropriate for collecting massive amounts of data within a short time. The open-ended question gave the respondents an opportunity to give a further opinion by qualifying or substantiating their answers. They were also intended to tap as much information as possible from the different categories of respondents.

2.7. Role of the Research—The researcher made a letter asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. After this, another letter of permission was secured and submitted to the participants. Upon approval, I used the forms of data collection as prescribed in the qualitative design. In this study, recording an in-depth interview was used. It was important for the researcher to get the subjective interaction between the study participants. The researcher heavily relied on naturalistic methods such as interviewing and audio recording, and the interpretive paradigm was used. Interpretive approaches rely heavily on naturalistic methods like interviewing, observation, and analysis of existing texts. These methods ensure an adequate dialog between the researchers and those with whom they interact in order to collaboratively construct a meaningful reality. Yin, as cited by Aquilam (2014), suggested numerous forms of data collection, including documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant observation, and physical artifacts. In order to have legitimate and trustworthy data on student-leaders experiences, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview. This interview aimed to explore the experiences of student-leaders in empowering leadership in school activities. The participants were encouraged to express their answers in their most comfortable manner. The interview with the learners

was transcribed word for word. Lastly, the researcher analyzed the data collected using discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Creswell (2007) suggested that succeeding in the conduct of the study; the data must be stored so that they can easily be found and protected from damage and loss.

2.8. Data Collection— The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission on the first week of December 2023 from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified schools. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with the attached Chapters 1 and 2 together with the research instrument, which explained the objectives of the study and the identification of the participants. The researcher waited for the response of the SDS before the conduct of it. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools during the third week of December, 2023. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants during the first week of January 2024. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire during the third week of January 2024. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. The researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder during the last week of January 2024. Since the

participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it to English. Data Coding and Thematizing. After the transcription, the data for the first and second weeks of February 2024 were categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual data within the participants were compared and contrasted to create patterns and trends.

2.9. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell’s Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data is common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis and involves generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding is not simply a method of data reduction; it was also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes, the researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each individual theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes. The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying its ‘essence’ and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name

for each theme. Writing-up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability are relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness instead of focusing on reliability and validity. Trustworthiness consists of components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility refers to the extent to which a research account is believable and appropriate, with particular reference to the level of agreement between participants and the researcher. The notion of credibility is most often associated with the framework presented by Yvonna Lincoln and Egon Guba. Transferability is the degree to which the results of qualitative research can be transferred to other contexts or settings with other respondents. The researcher facilitates the transferability judgment by a potential user through thick description. Dependability is the extent to which the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. Conformability refers to the objectivity of research during data collection and data analysis. There needs to be congruency between two or more independent persons about the accuracy, relevance, or meaning of the data (Polit Beck, 2012). Conformability also indicates a means to demonstrate quality. Confirmability associate’s objectivity in science with the use of instruments that are not dependent on human skill and perception. It was, however, difficult to ensure real objectivity since, as even tests and questionnaires were designed by humans, the intrusion of the researcher’s biases is inevitable.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

Here, steps must be taken to help ensure as far as possible that the work’s findings were the result of the experiences and ideas of the participants, rather than the characteristics and preferences of the researcher.

2.11. *Framework of the Analysis*—This study employed a qualitative research method. Rigorous and systematic steps are observed in analyzing the information gathered from the teacher-participants. Data were analyzed following the steps outlined by O’Connor and Gibson (2003) on qualitative data analysis: Organizing the Data. Data were organized in a way that was easy to look at and that allows the researcher to go through each topic to pick out concepts and themes. Finding and Organizing Ideas and Concepts. Find specific words or ideas keep coming up then organize these ideas into codes or categories.

Building Over-Arching Themes in the Data. Each of the response categories has one or more associated themes that give a deeper meaning to the data. Different categories can be collapsed under one main over-arching theme. Ensuring Reliability and Validity in the Data Analysis and in the Findings.

Findings are more dependable when they can be confirmed from several independent sources. Their validity is enhanced when they are confirmed by more than one “instrument” measuring the same thing. The researcher also completed the two other steps in this study: writing, which is drafting the output of the data analysis by weaving stories from narratives and literature, and presentation, which was the thematic and comprehensive presentation of output in artistic graphs and illustrations.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and their answers based on the responses of the participants. The participants unfolded their experiences and challenges as they engaged to empower leadership.

3.1. Experiences of Teachers in Promoting School Activities—In the context of promoting school activities, teachers play a crucial role in empowering student leaders and fostering a culture of leadership among students. Teachers can share their experiences and insights with student leaders, providing guidance and mentorship to help them effectively organize and lead school activities. Teachers can also facilitate leadership development workshops or training sessions to equip student leaders with the necessary skills and knowledge to succeed in their roles. By providing opportunities for students to take on leadership responsibilities and participate in decision-making processes, teachers empower students to become proactive and engaged members of the school community.

3.1.1. Role modeling—Role modeling by student leaders in school activities involves demonstrating positive behaviors, values, and attitudes for their peers to emulate. These leaders set an example through their actions, such as being respectful, responsible, and dedicated to their roles. By embodying these qualities, they inspire other students to do the same, creating a culture of excellence and leadership within the school community. The findings of the study agree with the findings of Nicole (2022) stating that participating in school activities as a student leader has several advantages. Female students can learn about gender barriers in leadership roles and develop their leadership skills through mentoring and role modeling from female school staff. Teachers and administrators play a major role in establishing a school's physical activity culture. Likewise, the study's findings are also supported by the study of Gerdy et al. (2020), through their influence over classroom procedures and development orientation, school leaders play a critical role in the effectiveness of their institutions, which in turn affects student achievement. The participants shared that these quotes emphasize the importance of unity and collaboration among leaders and their

peers in achieving common goals and overcoming challenges. The first quote highlighted how leaders not only provide direction but also foster unity among their team members. By working together and supporting each other, they can more effectively navigate through difficulties. The second quote reinforced the idea that unity brings strength to each individual, and every significant action taken contributes to positive change. Together, they possess the power to bring about significant impact. The third quote underscored the idea that every individual has a vital role to play in achieving collective objectives. Through collaboration and mutual support, they can accomplish more than they could alone. The fourth quote emphasized how leaders illuminate the path forward and guide their team towards success. Through unity, they can have a clearer direction and achieve their goals more effectively. Finally, the last quote highlights the concept of companionship and mutual assistance among leaders and their peers. By helping each other and working together, they can bring about meaningful change and achieve success collectively. These findings were consistent with the results of the study of Gregory and Carley (2022) to address issues such as legal liability and teacher disinterest in extracurricular leadership, teacher mentors serve as role models for healthy behavior. Teachers who act as role models can also help students develop their character by incorporating character education into the curriculum and setting an example of morality and behavior in the classroom (Jim and Christine, 2022).

3.1.2. Intensifying Communication—Communication in the context of student leaders' narratives in school activities revolves around the effective exchange of ideas, information, and goals among student leaders, teachers, and the broader school community. It involves verbal and non-verbal communication channels that facilitate understanding, collaboration, and empowerment. Student leaders utilize commu-

nication skills to articulate their vision, goals, and plans for school activities, effectively conveying their message to their peers and teachers. They engage in active listening to understand the needs and concerns of their fellow students, fostering a supportive and inclusive environment. When student leaders participate in school activities, effective communication has many benefits. According to the findings of the study of Jaycel et al. (2022), participation in student organizations fosters the development of verbal and nonverbal communication skills, subject knowledge, and organizational abilities. It can be gleaned from the responses of the participants the importance of unity, collaboration, and mutual support among student leaders in achieving their goals and driving positive change within the school community. The first quote highlights the idea that student leaders are not just individuals in positions of leadership but also companions who share a common understanding and purpose. Through unity, they draw strength from each other and commit to continuing their collaborative efforts toward bringing about positive change. The second quote reinforced the notion that success is achievable through unity. By coming together and working hand in hand, student leaders can effectively reach their dreams and aspirations, leveraging their collective strength and determination. The third quote underscored the idea of solidarity and mutual assistance among student leaders. It emphasized that they are not alone in their endeavors; they have companions who will support and trust them every step of the way, making their journey towards achieving their goals more manageable and meaningful. The foregoing results of the study were consistent with the findings made by Sharifah et al. (2022) building strong relationships within teams via communication facilitates the development of interpersonal connections, which in turn promotes team success.

3.1.3. Employing Output-oriented Approach—An output-oriented approach in narratives of student leaders in school activities with empowering leadership focuses on the tangible results and outcomes of their initiatives and endeavors. It involves setting clear goals, targets, and objectives, and working towards achieving them through focused effort and effective planning. In this approach, student leaders prioritize measurable results and impacts, such as increased student engagement, improved academic performance, or positive changes in the school environment. They adopt strategies and action plans that are directed towards producing specific outputs and driving meaningful changes within the school community. Research evidences show student leadership activities that employ output-oriented approaches have many advantages. Focusing on output helps students improve their ability to plan projects, reflect, solve problems, build teams, make decisions, set goals, manage time effectively, resolve conflicts, and have self-confidence. Furthermore, output is crucial for driving input in order to facilitate effective learning, particularly in language acquisition, according to the “output-driven hypothesis” according to the findings of the study of Ding and Wu (2018). The above responses explained how the power of unity, collaboration, and resilience among student leaders in achieving their goals and overcoming challenges within the school community. Statement 1 underscored the idea that unity among student leaders extends beyond individual interests to benefit everyone in the community. It emphasized the importance of collaboration and mutual support in achieving collective goals, highlighting that when student leaders work together, there are no limits to what they can achieve. While statement 2 highlighted the notion that challenges and setbacks present opportunities for growth and learning. It encourages student leaders to view every experience, whether positive or negative, as a lesson that contributes to

Fig. 3. Merging themes on the experiences of school leaders in promoting school activities

their progress and development. This mindset of resilience enables student leaders to persevere through difficulties and emerge stronger and more capable in their leadership roles. These findings were consistent with the results of the study by Ian and Neil (2024). This method facilitates the internalization of knowledge and skills by encouraging students to actively participate in practical tasks. Students can learn democratic practices and develop their leadership skills by participating in official decision-making processes in schools. Encouraging students to become effective leaders in a variety of school-related activities is made possible by an output-oriented approach to student leadership activities, which also helps to develop critical skills. Based on emerging themes in the experiences of school leaders in promoting school activities with a focus on empowering leadership through role modeling, intensifying communication, and employing output-oriented approach. In role

modeling, school leaders demonstrate effective leadership qualities through their actions, serving as role models for student leaders. School leaders uphold high standards of integrity and ethical conduct, inspiring student leaders to follow suit in their own leadership roles. Empower student leaders by delegating responsibilities, providing opportunities for growth, and fostering a culture of trust and accountability. For the second theme, intensifying communication established open and transparent communication channels, allowing for the exchange of ideas, feedback, and concerns between student leaders, teachers, and administrators. Actively listen to the needs and perspectives of student leaders, ensuring that their voices are heard and valued in decision-making processes. Communicate a clear vision and direction for school activities, enabling student leaders to align their efforts and work towards common goals.

In employing an output-oriented approach, school leaders set clear and achievable goals for school activities, providing student leaders with a roadmap for success. Monitor progress and evaluate outcomes of school activities, providing feedback and guidance to student leaders to ensure continuous improvement. Celebrate achievements and milestones in school activities, recognizing the efforts and contributions of student leaders and promoting a culture of

success and accomplishment.

3.2. *Coping Mechanisms with the Challenges in School Activities*—Balancing leadership responsibilities with academic studies, extracurricular activities, and personal commitments can be challenging for student leaders. They may struggle to allocate sufficient time and energy to fulfill their leadership roles effectively while also managing their other responsibilities. Student leaders may encounter

communication barriers when conveying their ideas, plans, and concerns to their peers, teachers, and school administrators. This can hinder collaboration and coordination efforts, leading to misunderstandings and inefficiencies in executing school activities. Furthermore, one of the primary challenges faced by empowered student leaders is balancing their academic commitments with their leadership responsibilities, according to the findings of Brown et al.'s study (2019). Juggling academic coursework, extracurricular activities, and leadership roles can be demanding and time-consuming, leading to stress and burnout among student leaders. Moreover, empowered student leaders often struggle with effectively managing their time to fulfill their leadership duties while also meeting academic deadlines and personal obligations, according to Drewry Doerman's (2018) findings. Prioritizing tasks, setting realistic goals, and maintaining a healthy work-life balance are essential skills that student leaders must develop to overcome this challenge.

3.2.1. Time Management—Time management in student leaders involves effectively organizing and prioritizing tasks to maximize productivity and meet deadlines. These leaders must balance their academic responsibilities with their roles in school activities, demonstrating the ability to allocate time wisely. By managing their time efficiently, they set a positive example for their peers and ensure the smooth execution of various events and initiatives. Effective time management is a key component of work-life balance, academic success, and general well-being for student leaders, based on the findings of the study by Anjana (2019). Furthermore, time management is necessary to lower stress levels, give one's life structure, and balance the competing demands of extracurricular activities and study (Subramanian, 2019). Effective time management is viewed as a critical component of educational improvement in the context of school organizations dealing with is-

ues like resource scarcity and social vices as stated by Chima (2018). Thus, in order for student leaders to increase their productivity and effectively mentor their peers in school activities, they must cultivate strong time management attitudes. The responses above shed light on some of the challenges encountered by student leaders in their leadership roles within school activities. The first statement highlighted the challenge of fostering unity among all sectors of the school community. Student leaders often face the task of bringing together diverse groups of individuals, including students, teachers, and administrators, to work towards common goals. Building unity requires effective communication, collaboration, and inclusivity to overcome differences and build a cohesive team. The second statement underscored the importance of coordination and consultation in navigating through differing opinions and disagreements. Student leaders must invest time and effort in ensuring that all stakeholders are involved in decision-making processes and that their perspectives are considered. This requires patience, diplomacy, and effective communication skills to reach a consensus and move projects forward. The present findings of the study were consistent with the result findings that effective time management is essential to student leaders' performance and achievement in school-related activities. Studies reveal that proficient time management has a favourable influence on scholastic achievements these findings is congruent to the notion of a comprehensive study by Jerald and John (2019) and is closely linked to enhanced academic performance (Maria et al., 2021)

3.2.2. Dealing with passive members—Dealing with passive members in student leaders in school activities requires patience, understanding, and proactive engagement. Leaders should strive to motivate and inspire passive members by involving them in discussions, assigning specific tasks, and providing opportu-

nities for their input. By fostering a supportive and inclusive environment, leaders can encourage passive members to become more engaged and contribute actively to the success of the group. It can be difficult to deal with passive student leaders in school activities. The study's findings agree with Salamakha's (2021). Research has shown that passive participation in cooperative online learning activities has a variety of effects on learning outcomes and calls for the use of engagement-boosting pedagogical strategies. Likewise, the study's findings are also supported by the study of Ha-Eun and Jaesung (2023). The participants opened up with statement 3, revealing the difficulty of building trust and respect for our leadership is also evident. There are students who are not convinced of our decisions, and we need to understand why and how they feel that way. This statement highlights that the challenges faced by the student leader extend beyond just fostering unity. It acknowledged the importance of trust and respect for effective leadership. The leader recognizes the presence of dissenting opinions among students and emphasizes the need to comprehend the reasons behind these sentiments. Statement 5, commented on the leader reflects on their experiences and acknowledges the numerous obstacles encountered while carrying out their responsibilities. They specifically highlight the difficulty of unifying various segments or groups within the school community, indicating the importance of cohesion for effective leadership. This statement 6 emphasizes the significance of coordination and communication in overcoming differences and disagreements among individuals with varying opinions. It underscores the necessity of clear and effective communication channels to ensure successful project completion despite divergent viewpoints. Statement 7 encapsulates the idea that challenges and trials are inherent in leadership roles. It suggests that each obstacle presents an opportunity for growth and learning. The leader

acknowledges that facing challenges and trials is an integral part of the leadership journey, and each experience contributes to personal and professional development. This statement 10 emphasizes the collaborative nature of leadership. It conveys the idea that leadership is not a solitary endeavor but rather involves the collective effort of the entire community. By highlighting the importance of unity and solidarity, the leader emphasizes that progress and continuity depend on the cooperation and support of all members of the community. On the other hand, in order to guarantee active participation in the group process, group leaders working with involuntary and negative members need to employ particular skills and interventions the findings were consistent with the results of the study by Christine and Ed (2019). Addressing and resolving this issue requires an understanding of the motivational factors and behavioral patterns that underlie passive behavior (Andreas et al., 2019). Furthermore, the necessity of involving passive followers in order to preserve productive leader-member relationships is highlighted by the movement in organizational emotion management from leadership to followership the findings of the study were affirmed by the study of Erika et al. (2020). In general, addressing passive members in student leaders entails identifying their motivations and behaviors as well as putting strategies into place to improve their engagement and contribution to group activities.

3.2.3. Resilience and resourcefulness— Limited resources present a significant challenge for student leaders in their efforts to promote school activities with empowering leadership. These constraints may include insufficient funding, inadequate facilities, and a shortage of manpower, all of which can hinder the planning and execution of projects and initiatives. Student leaders must navigate these limitations creatively, finding innovative solutions and leveraging available resources effectively to maximize their impact. Despite the challenges posed by

limited resources, student leaders can still foster a culture of empowerment by prioritizing collaboration, creativity, and inclusivity, ensuring that all members of the school community have the opportunity to contribute and participate in meaningful ways. By overcoming resource constraints through resilience and resourcefulness, student leaders demonstrate their ability to lead with vision and purpose, inspiring others to join them in creating positive change within the school environment. Limited resources for student leaders can impact school activities in a number of ways. The way that students view their resources has a big impact on their social inclusion, academic self-concept, and overall well-being. The present findings of the study were consistent with the results of Martiman (2021). Participants expressed their concerns about limited school resources, but these did not hinder them from performing their roles as student leaders. Their attitude and commitment made them resilient and resourceful through unity and collaboration. Students' sense of ownership, responsibility, and accountability can be fostered in the classroom by involving them in leadership activities that make use of their talents and skills; likewise, the study's findings are also supported by Darryl (2018). Furthermore, encouraging students' creativity by assigning them to make musical instruments out of limited supplies can aid in removing obstacles to their ability to think creatively, which is an essential leadership trait as stated by Janka et al. (2021). As a result, addressing the lack of resources through instruction, imaginative endeavors, and

the development of student leaders can improve their general growth and have a favorable effect on school activities. Based on the emerging themes, the coping mechanisms with the challenges in school activities were time management, dealing with passive members, and resilience and resourcefulness. The emerging themes of time management, dealing with passive members, resilience, and resource lessness present significant challenges for student leaders who have been empowered with leadership responsibilities in school activities. Effective time management is crucial as student leaders balance their leadership roles with academic studies, extracurricular activities, and personal commitments. They must prioritize tasks, set deadlines, and allocate time wisely to ensure the successful planning and execution of school activities. Dealing with passive members poses another challenge, as student leaders may encounter individuals who are reluctant to actively participate or contribute to group efforts. Student leaders must employ strategies to engage and motivate passive members, fostering a sense of ownership and accountability within the team. Additionally, limited resources, such as funding, facilities, and manpower, present obstacles that student leaders must overcome through creativity, innovation, and effective resource allocation. Despite these challenges, student leaders can develop resilience, problem-solving skills, and teamwork abilities, ultimately strengthening their leadership capabilities and driving positive change within the school community.

3.3. Insights Can Be Drawn from The Findings of The Study of Student Leaders in Their Leadership Journey—The study's findings offer valuable insights for educational management, which can update strategic decisions and foster a culture of continuous improvement. Student leaders thrive when they are empow-

ered with responsibilities and granted the autonomy to make decisions. Empowerment fosters a sense of ownership and commitment among student leaders, leading to increased engagement and effectiveness in their leadership roles. Collaboration among student leaders, teachers, and other stakeholders is essential for the success

Fig. 4. Emerging themes on the coping mechanisms with the challenges in school activities

of school activities. Working together enables student leaders to leverage diverse perspectives, skills, and resources, resulting in more innovative and impactful initiatives.

3.3.1. Empowering leaders—Empowering leaders in student leaders in school activities involves fostering a sense of autonomy, responsibility, and confidence within the team. These leaders encourage others to take initiative, make decisions, and contribute their ideas to the group’s success. By creating an environment where everyone’s voice is valued and respected, empowering leaders inspire a sense of ownership and motivation among their peers. There are many advantages to giving leaders in student activities more power the result were consistent with the major findings of Bryan (2023). Schools can prioritize well-being, establish student-led learning communities, and make sure all voices are heard by putting autonomy-supportive leadership training into practice, as stated by Nur et al. (2023). Some participants shared insights on empowering leaders. As revealed by the participants, P1 emphasized that leadership encompasses problem-solving and knowledge-sharing beyond just achieving goals. P2 highlighted the personal growth and progress achieved through overcoming obstacles. P8 asserted that every leader possesses the capability to contribute to a better future for their school and community. P9 reflected on how both successes and failures strengthen leaders. P10 un-

derscored that leadership is not only a responsibility but also an opportunity to inspire others. Creating student leadership teams (Andrea and Kyle, 2019) enhances students’ active participation in their education and communities while supporting student agency and self-advocacy. This is in line with the personalized learning trend.

3.3.2. Fostering Stakeholders Support—Stakeholder support in student leaders in school activities involves engaging and collaborating with various groups such as teachers, parents, and the community. These leaders seek input and feedback from stakeholders to ensure their activities align with broader goals and values. By fostering strong relationships and partnerships, student leaders can gain valuable resources, guidance, and initiative support. This insight transmits substantial associations for educational management. Numerous advantages result from stakeholders supporting student leaders in school-related activities. When stakeholders actively participate in programs, program utilization increases, and student behavior and well-being improve. The study’s findings agree with Hmina’s (2022), Khoiriyah, and Ratu (2019) findings. P3 emphasized that effective leadership involves garnering support, understanding, and addressing the needs of stakeholders to strengthen unity. P7 highlighted how challenges present opportunities for leaders to mobilize stakeholder support and facilitate

change. A supportive school leadership cultivates a positive school culture and climate while having a positive impact on student learning and school development. The results were consistent with the major findings made by Soribel (2023). Participants from stakeholders can also improve staff motivation, communication, efficiency in school management, teaching and learning, and ultimately, school performance and student accomplishments, similarly highlighted by Ira et al. (2019). In addition, the execution of Psycho-social Support (PSS) initiatives has the potential to greatly augment stakeholder involvement, foster a feeling of inclusion, and elevate the caliber and impartiality of education within the educational community (Fidaa Mazen, 2022). Stakeholder support is essential for empowering student leaders and improving the school environment as a whole.

3.3.3. Promoting unity and collaboration—Promoting unity and collaboration in narratives of student leaders in school activities with empowering leadership involves fostering a sense of belonging, inclusivity, and teamwork among students, teachers, and other stakeholders. Student leaders play a pivotal role in facilitating open communication, building trust, and encouraging collective decision-making to ensure that everyone's voices are heard and valued. By promoting unity and collaboration, student leaders create an environment where diverse perspectives are embraced, and individuals work together towards common goals, ultimately leading to greater student engagement, enhanced problem-solving abilities, and the achievement of shared objectives within the school community. Student performance is improved when schools use the Team of Teams model, which is led by individuals who exhibit transparency and teamwork, fostering a positive culture, as revealed by Maria and Konstantinos (2021). A supportive environment for growth and success is created by collaborative leadership, born out of complex interactions between staff members, students, and teachers and is motivated by individual goals. Carol et al. (2019) also supports the study's findings. Collaborative leadership also encourages creativity and independence among employees. P4's insight suggested that student authorities have the potential to take the lead in finding solutions to school-related issues, positioning them as key players in addressing challenges within the educational environment. P5 emphasized the importance of understanding students' circumstances and needs as a means to identify areas for improvement and effectively address school issues. P6 underscored the value of altruism, highlighting how helping others not only brings personal satisfaction but also adds meaning and significance to one's own life. In school activities, there are many advantages to encouraging harmony and cooperation among student leaders. When students are involved in every stage of the intervention, they work more cooperatively with teachers and one another, going above and beyond the original goals based on the study findings of Bity et al. (2021). Furthermore, supporting a cooperative network between educators, learners, and the community improves the delivery of civic education since educators who work in courteous, cooperative settings are more likely to give citizenship education top priority to their students (Fernando, 2019). Based on the emerging themes, insights can be drawn from the findings of the study of student leaders in their leadership journey. Empowering leaders, fostering stakeholders' support, and promoting unity and collaboration are the three themes. The study reveals the significance of empowering student leaders with responsibilities and autonomy, allowing them to make decisions and take action. Empowered leaders are more likely to demonstrate confidence, initiative, and creativity in addressing challenges and driving positive change within the school community. In fostering stakeholders' support, the findings underscore the importance of stakeholders' support, including teach-

Fig. 5. Emerging themes on the insights can be drawn from the findings of the study of student leaders in their leadership journey

ers, administrators, parents, and fellow students, achieve their goals. The study highlights the role of student leaders in promoting unity and collaboration among diverse groups within the school community. When student leaders receive backing from various stakeholders, they are better equipped to implement their ideas, overcome obstacles, and

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents the study and findings summary, from which I drew the implications and future directions. My study aimed to learn about student leaders' experiences, challenges, and insights into promoting school activities by empowering leadership. I used a qualitative phenomenological method and thematic analysis to achieve the research objectives. In adherence to Creswell's (2006) guidelines, open-ended interview questions were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through the interview approach, I encouraged my participants to discuss their definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored, which were the experiences of student leaders fully and openly in school activities.

4.1. Findings—The findings revealed that student leaders serve as role models by demonstrating positive behaviors and values, inspiring their peers to follow suit and fostering unity and resilience within the school community. Effective communication is vital for student leaders to articulate their vision, convey goals, and engage with peers and teachers, facilitating understanding, collaboration, and the execution of school activities. Focusing on achieving tangible results by setting clear goals and employing effective planning strategies helps student leaders enhance engagement and improve the school environment. Balancing leadership responsibilities with academic and personal commitments is challenging, making effective time management crucial for student leaders to fulfill their roles successfully. Engaging passive members and building trust are essential for fostering a cohesive team, requiring student leaders to understand the reasons behind passive behavior and work towards motivating such members. Overcoming limited resources through creativity and innovation is necessary, demonstrating resilience by finding ways to maximize the impact of available resources. Empowering student leaders with autonomy and responsibility fosters a sense of ownership and commitment,

enhancing their engagement and effectiveness. Collaboration among student leaders, teachers, and stakeholders is crucial for the success of school activities, with diverse perspectives and skills contributing to more innovative and impactful initiatives.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. On the experiences of student leaders in promoting school activities with a focus on empowering leadership through role modeling, intensifying communication, and employing an output-oriented approach. In role modeling, school leaders demonstrate practical leadership qualities through their actions, serving as role models for student leaders. School leaders uphold high standards of integrity and ethical conduct, inspiring student leaders to follow suit in their leadership roles. Empower student leaders by delegating responsibilities, providing opportunities for growth, and fostering a culture of trust and accountability. To intensify communication, student leaders should establish open and transparent communication channels to exchange ideas, feedback, and concerns between student leaders, teachers, and administrators. They should also actively listen to student leaders' needs and perspectives, ensuring their voices are heard and valued in decision-making. Finally, they should communicate a clear vision and direction for school activities, enabling student leaders to align their efforts and work towards common goals. In an output-oriented approach, student leaders set clear and achievable goals for school activities, providing student leaders with a roadmap for success. Monitor progress and evaluate outcomes of school activities, providing feedback and guidance to student leaders to ensure continuous improvement. Celebrate achievements and milestones in school activities, recognizing the efforts and contributions of student leaders and promoting a culture of success and accomplishment. On coping mechanisms with the challenges in school activities,

themes identified were time management, dealing with passive members, resilience, and resourcefulness. The emerging themes of time management, dealing with passive members, and resilience and resourcefulness present significant challenges for student leaders who have been empowered with leadership responsibilities in school activities. Effective time management was crucial as student leaders balance their leadership roles with academic studies, extracurricular activities, and personal commitments. They must prioritize tasks, set deadlines, and allocate time wisely to ensure the successful planning and execution of school activities. Dealing with passive members poses another challenge, as student leaders may encounter individuals who are reluctant to participate or contribute to group efforts actively. Student leaders must employ strategies to engage and motivate passive members, fostering a sense of ownership and accountability within the team. Additionally, limited resources, such as funding, facilities, and manpower, present obstacles that student leaders must overcome through creativity, innovation, and effective resource allocation. Despite these challenges, student leaders can develop resilience, problem-solving skills, and teamwork abilities, ultimately strengthening their leadership capabilities and driving positive change within the school community. Insights drawn from the findings of the study of student leaders in their leadership journey were empowering leaders, fostering stakeholders' support, and promoting unity and collaboration. Empowering leaders, the study reveals the significance of empowering student leaders with responsibilities and autonomy, allowing them to make decisions and take action. Empowered leaders are likelier to demonstrate confidence, initiative, and creativity in addressing challenges and driving positive change within the school community. In fostering stakeholders' support, the findings underscore the importance of stakeholders' support, including teachers, administra-

tors, parents, and fellow students, in the success of student leaders' initiatives. When student leaders receive backing from various stakeholders, they are better equipped to implement their ideas, overcome obstacles, and achieve their goals. In promoting unity and collaboration, the study highlights the role of student leaders in promoting unity and collaboration among diverse groups within the school community. By fostering a sense of belonging, inclusivity, and teamwork, student leaders create an environment where individuals work together towards common objectives, leading to enhanced student engagement, problem-solving, and collective achievement. These insights emphasize the transformative potential of empowering leaders' and stakeholders' support and promoting unity and collaboration in student leadership development. By embracing these principles, student leaders can effectively navigate their leadership journey, inspire others, and drive meaningful change within their school and beyond. Empowering student leaders fosters a sense of ownership and investment in school activities among the student body. When students feel empowered to take initiative and contribute to decision-making processes, they are more likely to actively engage in school events, initiatives, and programs. By sharing narratives of empowered student leaders, schools can inspire and encourage other students to take on leadership roles. These narratives serve as examples of effective leadership practices, providing valuable insights and guidance for aspiring student leaders in developing their leadership skills and abilities. The narratives of student leaders in school activities with empowering leadership have profound implications for leadership development, student engagement, school culture, problem-solving, and community relationships. By embracing and promoting empowering leadership practices, schools can cultivate a positive

and vibrant learning environment that nurtures the potential of all students.

4.2.1. Future Directions—The study's findings should be properly relayed and used by the significant people for whom this research was intended. School principals and administrators may use the research findings to inform the development of school policies and practices that support student leadership and collaboration. This may include policies related to student representation, decision-making processes, and the allocation of resources for student-led initiatives. They may also organize workshops or training sessions for school principals, teachers, and other educators to familiarize them with the study's findings. **Student Leaders.** They may develop or enhance student leadership programs within schools, incorporating the principles of empowering leadership identified in the study. They should provide opportunities for students to develop leadership skills and engage in collaborative decision-making processes. **The Learners** may implement student engagement initiatives that facilitate dialogue and collaboration among students, teachers, and other stakeholders. This could involve organizing forums, workshops, or focus groups where students can share their experiences as leaders and contribute ideas for improving school activities. **Other Stakeholders.** They may share the research findings with other stakeholders, such as parents, school board members, and community leaders, to raise awareness of the importance of empowering student leadership. **Future Researchers.** They may collaborate with researchers and institutions to research student leadership and empowerment further. Future studies could explore additional aspects of empowering leadership, examine its long-term impact on student outcomes, or investigate effective strategies for promoting collaboration and inclusivity within school settings.

5. References

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